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ON THE TEACHING OF ĀYURVEDA

In the past four years the courses on Āyurveda consisted mainly of translating a number of Sanskrit medical texts and their commentaries. The procedure was that for each session one of the students prepared a piece of the text and presented his interpretation which was then discussed in the group. The texts included chapters of the Mādhavanīdāna not yet translated and the treatment of cataract-surgery in the three saṃhitās. Two chapters of Suśruta's Sūtrasthāna were translated — both with Ḍalhaṇa's comments — and also Nīdāna 1 (the etiology of wind-diseases) with Gayadāsa's commentary. Part of this latter chapter was chosen for presentation to you because it illustrates a number of the problems students have to deal with. Such problems are the subject of this talk.

First, of course, the commentary presented difficulties which are inherent to the style rather than to the subject dealt with. A sound introduction-manual is absolutely necessary : it should deal not only with the particularities of the commentator's language, but also with the more technical aspects which practically every commentary incorporates. For instance, in the field of grammar, their way of formulating the derivation and etymology of words, their explanation of indeclinables, etc. The existing grammatical dictionaries tend to confront the layman with a bewildering variety of explanations. On other aspects, such as those pertaining to the traditional Indian way of dealing with texts, the student would have to consult a number of existing translations in order to understand what the commentator is aiming at : instances are their explanations of such words as 'atha' (now..) at the beginning of a work or chapter, the different levels of authority they apply to paragraphs, etc. A systematic treatment of the major resources of the commentator's toolbox would benefit everyone who has to cope with this particular style.

Then there are the problems regarding the contents of medical works. The lack of specialised dictionaries has already been indicated. Nobody will doubt the fact that progress in the study of Āyurveda is seriously hampered by this lack. From a didactic point of view there is another desideratum which would serve other specialists as well : a systematic, guided approach to the central theories and technical terms of Āyurveda. One might think about compiling an annotated translation of selected pieces from various sources. Such a sourcebook should, however, be accompanied by visual materials: in particular the techniques used in Āyurveda are often difficult to under-

stand from the bare text and should be demonstrated on film or video. Our experience was that the text-sequences on cataract-surgery became intelligible only after seeing such an operation on video – performed in the west, but still most instructive for those of us who did not have a sound idea of such elementary facts as the physical composition of the eye's outer surface, etc. When a project of recording Ayurvedic techniques is undertaken, care should be taken to present in a lucid fashion both the written tradition (a particular surgical operation should be known from the texts well before the recording is done) and also the medical specialist's comments and personal opinions on the techniques he performs.

For the ordinary Indologist it is practically impossible to master the intricacies of botany, nosology and anatomy. Our experience, at least, was that even the most basic data in this field had to be explained to us by Dr. Meulenbeld. It is, however, conceivable that a basic knowledge of these fields is necessary, not only to be able to make acceptable translations, but especially to be able to cooperate with other specialists. From Dr. Meindersma's lecture it is clear that very much the same problem arises for these other specialists. A possible solution may lie in the founding of an international training-institute, on a post-graduate level, where the relevant specialisations are explained in such a way that mutual understanding becomes feasible. But perhaps the present public could offer other ideas to cope with this and the aforementioned topics.